

MANAGEMENT BY OBJECTIVES AND PERFORMANCE OF PARKLANE HOSPITAL, ENUGU

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Abstract: The study evaluated management by objectives (MBO) and the performance of Parklane Hospital, Enugu. The specific objectives were to: evaluate the effect of setting objectives on the operational efficiency and identify the effect of developing action plans on the waste reduction of Parklane hospital, Enugu. The target population of the study consists of one thousand, one hundred and fifty-one (1,151) senior and junior staff of the hospital. The adequate sample size, of 288 staff was adopted using Freund and Williams's statistical formula at 5 percent margin of error. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary sources of data were the administration of questionnaire. 245 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and Pearson correlation (r) were used to test the hypotheses. The results showed that Setting objectives had significant positive relationship with the operational efficiency $r(95, n = 245), .450 < .769 = p. < 0.05$. Developing action plans had significant positive relationship with the waste reduction, $r(95, n = 245), .479 < .719 = p. < 0.05$ of Parklane hospital, Enugu. The study concluded that setting objectives and developing action plans had positive significant relationship with the operational efficiency and waste reduction. The study recommended among others that Organizational objectives should be stated to all employees at the initial time of recruitment in other to avoid lapses.

Keywords: Management, Objectives, MBO Performance, Parklane Hospital.

Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

Conventional management practices include management by objectives (MBO). Since the issue was originally covered in articles in the latter part of the 20th century by both scientists and practitioners, the method is well-known and heavily pushed. A strategic management strategy called management by objectives (MBO) seeks to raise an organization's performance via the establishment of well-defined goals that are supported by both management and staff. The creation of a management information system (MIS) to compare actual performance and accomplishments to the specified objectives is known as management by objectives, or management by planning (Drury, 2021). Precise work objectives or targets are used to create awareness of results in the more "democratic" and potentially successful MBO method. Indeed, there appears to be a fashion trend when it comes to establishing particular employment requirements in white-collar and service industries. As part of the Management by Objectives (MBO) human management approach, managers and staff collaborate to establish,

document, and track goals over a predetermined time frame. Planning and organizational objectives are top-down processes that are transformed into individual goals for each organizational member (Grimsley, 2021). It is noteworthy that MBO is closely linked to the positive management concept. By virtue of its favorably interpreted management actions (i.e., mutually accepted objectives, autonomy in identifying and utilizing ways to attain goals, self-control, and occasionally collaborative control work by team members), the MBO model empowers employees. As a successful means of inspiring workers, it promotes the accomplishment of other management responsibilities (planning, coordinating, and controlling). Goal management makes employees more motivated to work hard and achieve company goals (Bieniok et al., 2004). The literature on positive management provides several instances of how management uses goals to sway workers. In his writing, Chodorek discusses goal management in the context of a positive superior-inferior dynamic (Chodorek, 2010). Another author, Szelagowska-Rudzka, examines a problem with team participation in running a very inspiring company. Thus, goal management is a process that comprises carrying out tasks, making decisions, and fixing organizational issues while encouraging the use of a team engagement concept (Szelagowska-Rudzka, 2015).

With a few deviations, this strategy is results-driven and nearly identical to the approach to job standards. The manager and employee then take a seat together to decide on priorities for the period. When it comes time for the performance review, the manager and employee have a discussion about the goals that have been set and determine whether or not they have been met. The open communication between the manager and the employee is an advantage of this. The employee frequently has "buy-in" because they helped establish the objectives, and the assessment may be a vehicle for further ability development. This strategy works well for jobs that are not routine and call for a higher degree of mental effort to do. For MBOs to be successful, employees and managers need to be able to write compelling objectives. It's common knowledge that utilizing goal management to evaluate a team's performance presents a problem. The example comes from a study done with health care teams, where researchers showed that MBO had a beneficial effect on the success of the team (Adorian et al., 1990).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is beneficial for organizations, including employees, to establish sensible aims generally. The standards are passed on to the employees and they are trained to meet the goal. Guidelines are designed to evaluate personnel and monitor the primary causes of any departure from the expectations set. Monitoring the duties and responsibilities carried out by staff members, seeing any ambiguity, and putting things back on course. It is indicated how the actual measured performance compares to the benchmarks and criteria. The comparison highlights any variations from the standards and demonstrates how the workforce has met the established objectives. This disparity indicates whether the performance is above, below, or in line with the standards. A major component of this stage is measuring performance and conducting evaluations, comparisons, and analyses. Discussion on Findings: In this forum, managers and staff members talk about a range of situations and abilities related to their jobs, as well as professional development, planning, and making decisions based on the assessment's findings.

The problems with management by objectives (MBO) include poor employee-management joint planning, a breakdown in joint control, a lack of goal-setting, a lack of support from upper management, resentful attitudes among subordinates, difficulties quantifying goals and objectives, time-consuming and expensive processes, a focus on short-term goals, and a lack of appropriate skills and training that will improve hospital performance. If these issues are not properly treated, it will lead to poor quality of service, lack of employee commitment and

employee punctuality to work. Based on this, the study evaluates the effect of management by objectives (MBO) on the employee performance of Parklane Hospital in Enugu metropolis.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of management by objectives (MBO) and the performance of Parklane Hospital, Enugu. The specific objectives were to:

- ❖ Evaluate the relationship between setting objectives and the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu.
- ❖ Identify the relationship between developing action plans and the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- ❖ What is the relationship between setting objectives and the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu?
- ❖ ii. What is the relationship between developing action plans and the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu?

1.5 Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study.

- i. Setting objectives have relationship with the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu.
- ii. Developing action plans have relationship with the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study based on the relationship of management by objectives (MBO) and the performance of Parklane Hospital, Enugu. The study made use of dependent and independent variables. The independent variables include; setting objectives and developing action plans used in the study while operational efficiency and waste reduction of Parklane hospital, Enugu, were dependent variables. Time scope of the study was 2019 – 2023.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Management

A given or predetermined aim or target can only be effectively achieved with the collaboration, participation, intervention, and engagement of others, which is why management is a social activity. The Italian verb "maneggiare," which literally translates as "to handle" or "train horses," is where the word "management" originates. Thus, according to its etymology, it implies to manage, guide, direct, and lead economically (Amadi, 2018). Authorized personnel establish, maintain, and run an organization in order to choose and fulfill its goals through the integrating process of management. It is the process of guiding or directing individuals toward the aims and objectives of an organization (Sapre, 2014). The art of management is using people to accomplish goals. According to Connolly, James, and Fertig (2017), management entails defining an organization's strategy and organizing staff members' efforts to achieve goals by utilizing all available resources, including financial, natural, technical, and human resources.

The process of enabling a workflow in an integrated and coordinated way to achieve the specific goals through the efficient use of fabric resources is known as management. Management frequently benefits from planning how to use financial, human, and physical resources for corporate operations in a way that achieves the established objectives. Planning, organizing, staffing, directing, and regulating organizational resources allow management

to successfully and efficiently accomplish organizational goals. Among the most significant occupations in human existence is managing. People began organizing into groups in order to pursue goals that could not be completed individually. Any organization's management is its vital component. You will need to master a number of abilities, such as organization, leadership, communication, and planning, if you want to be an efficient manager. In order to guide staff, sales, and other activities toward achieving the company's objectives, you will also need to have in-depth understanding of those objectives. Nisha (2021). Whether a company, non-profit, or governmental entity, management is the administration of that entity. An organization's management tasks include formulating its strategy and organizing the work of its staff or volunteers to achieve its goals by utilizing all available resources, including human, financial, natural, and technical resources. Managers are another group of persons to whom the term "management" may apply. In order to contribute to an enterprise's success, management entails determining the mission, aim, processes, regulations, and manipulation of the enterprise's human resource (Lumineau & Oliveira, 2017).

2.1.2 Objectives

The precise activities and quantifiable stages your business must take to accomplish its goals are known as objectives. Within a company, the seniority hierarchy of employees may also be referred to as management. They provide you with a clear picture of the particular jobs or initiatives that must be finished in order to move your company closer to the goal. Although goals and objectives are two separate ideas, they complement one other to help you reach your goals and increase team productivity. Setting goals without specific objectives results in goals that are never reached (Range 2019).

2.1.3 Management by Objectives

A strategic management strategy called management by objectives (MBO) seeks to raise an organization's performance via the establishment of well-defined goals that are supported by both management and staff. The notion states that giving employees a vote in goal-setting and action plans promotes involvement and commitment from them as well as aims to be aligned throughout the business (Adam, 2021). A method for raising employee performance called "management by objectives" involves management and staff working together to establish goals. The notion suggests that one strategy to promote increased performance and commitment among employees is to solicit their opinion on goals and action plans (Perform Yard, 2019).

2.1.4. Setting of Specific Goals

For more than 35 years, goal-setting has been acknowledged as a potent motivator in a wide range of clinical and real-world contexts. "The object or aim of an action, for example, to attain a specific standard of proficiency, usually within a specified time limit," is what Latham and Locke (2002, p. 705) define as "goals." They represent the degree of proficiency we hope to reach and serve as a helpful prism through which to view how we are doing right now. The method through which we accomplish these goals is called goal setting. According to Locke (2019), "Every person's life depends on the process of choosing goals to pursue; if you remain passive you are not going to thrive as a human being," the significance of the goal-setting process should not be undervalued. The foundation of goal-setting theory (Locke & Latham, 1984) is the idea that intentional goals influence behavior (Ryan, 1970) and that intentional human activity is driven by personal objectives. To put it simply, we have to choose what is best for our personal wellbeing and then make objectives to get it (Elaine 2020).

2.1.5 Developing action plans

An action plan is a road map that will assist you in achieving the aims and objectives of your program. A program can follow several paths to attain goals, meet objectives, and produce results, just as there are various ways to get to a place when traveling.

The road maps that a program utilizes to fulfill its goals and objectives are called action plans. Add the three essential components. Typically, action plans consist of the questions "what," "who," and "when." They describe the course of action (the "what") that your program will follow in order to accomplish your goals and objectives, the person or people who will be in charge (the "who"), and the anticipated dates of completion (the "when"). Action plans, above all, emphasize the "why" behind a program aim. Research pushes us to highlight the "why" in planning and motivates others to collaborate with us to operationalize plans and achieve objectives. Simon Sinek reminds us that understanding the reason of an activity encourages a better feeling of purpose and initiative in people conducting the task in *Start with Why: How Great Leaders Inspire Everyone to Take Action* (Sinek, 2019).

The process of putting your strategy and objectives into practice is called action planning. Taking your concepts and organizing the means to bring them to life. Stated differently, action planning involves determining the precise steps required to reach your desired destination. It doesn't matter if they are organizational or personal goals the necessary abilities remain the same. The finest plans, in life or at work, incorporate action planning into their strategic thinking. Ultimately, the efficacy of a plan is negated if it remains unimplemented. Thus, one of the most important components of the strategic abilities one needs is action planning.

2.1.6 Performance

The act of putting on a play, concert, or other type of entertainment is called a performance. It can also refer to the act of performing or finishing a task, activity, or function. Job performance in the workplace refers to the assumed definition or specifications of a role. Task and contextual work performances are the two categories. Cognitive aptitude determines task performance, but personality determines contextual performance. Task performance is linked to responsibilities in behavior that are identified in job descriptions and pay structures. While contextual performances are value-based and add extra behavioral roles that are not covered by compensation or recognized in job descriptions, they are directly related to organizational performance. In contrast, extra roles that are indirectly related to organizational performance are contextual performances (Wikipedia, 2021). Every business has a set of desired overall outcomes that it hopes to achieve. Members may get the findings inferred from them or directly communicated to them. Carpenter (2021). Researchers and management teams have long been interested in evaluating an organization's success. Furthermore, evaluating corporate performance in the current economic climate is a crucial concern for researchers and working managers (Omar & Zineb, 2019). When carried out regularly with appropriate criteria, it aims to provide the administration level feedback that is required (Argon, 2004). When an organization's goals are completed and each member's contribution to the company is assessed, performance evaluation is very important (Ludeman, 2000; Nizamettin & Gokhan 2008).

2.1.7. Operational efficiency

Patient happiness and service value can both be enhanced by operational efficiency. With growing healthcare expenses and restricted access to resources, providing the best treatment possible remains a problem. More patient-centered healthcare is required in today's healthcare system. Patient satisfaction is the cornerstone of the

patient-centered approach to assessing and improving health (Grondahl et al., 2016). According to Ancarani et al. (2011), a patient's assessment of their entire experience following the receipt of medical services is known as their patient satisfaction. Patients now choose their doctors more actively, and both doctors and patients themselves are increasingly concerned with providing patients with patient-centered care (Senot, Chandrasekaran & Ward, 2016).

Operational efficiency guarantees that health systems function effectively while providing patients with appropriate and high-quality care. It is anticipated that the healthcare industry will undergo some operational performance improvements that contribute to the improvement of cost, quality, flexibility, efficiency, effectiveness, and other metrics of health organizations. Improving work processes in healthcare organizations contributes to improved health outcomes, increased efficiency, and resource optimization (AzyatiAnualet' al 2018).

The planning and structuring of a business's financial, administrative, and operational procedures with the goal of optimizing internal resource allocation is known as operations management. The legal operations of a hospital, specialty practice, auxiliary care provider, or remote health service center, as well as the clinical activities that maintain patient care within the health system, are all included in healthcare operations. The lives of individuals are at risk in the health care sector. There is more to efficient healthcare operations management than just increasing output and profit margins. In order to eventually save and enhance lives, health care operations methods and software enable the effective supply and delivery of healthcare services to patients and communities. Enhancing operations management is essential for every organization's development and success. Since the health care sector is a service sector, it makes sense for businesses to strive toward standardizing protocol in order to enhance performance. Enhancing clinical care management can lead to better patient relationships and a decrease in readmissions. By creating goods and services more quickly than rivals, a business may optimize the use of its resources through the technique of operational effectiveness. In addition to lowering these burdensome expenses, operational efficiency raises patient happiness and service value. Long-term patient benefits may result from fostering collaboration between healthcare providers and health insurance firms to decide on the scope of medical coverage and the prompt payment of service fees. However, because it is challenging to sustain revenues and market share, hospitals face fierce competition in their quest to offer the finest services (Capkun et al., 2012). The creation of the emergency department (ED) at every hospital has been found to cause a periodic growth in the number of patients and customers, and the process of improving these healthcare facilities' operational performance is becoming more complex. Due to significant government funding, public tertiary health institutions often do not compete with private healthcare services (Suki, Lian & Suki, 2011). Consequently, Nerninathan et al. (2014) suggested that health care providers think about using operational management to reduce waste in order to limit expenditure and any growing prices. Data on certain healthcare-related activities are collected, measured, and evaluated for healthcare performance assessments. Their goal is to locate areas where expenses may be cut while simultaneously enhancing service delivery efficiency and quality.

In the context of patient-centered healthcare, operational efficiency is a crucial component of experience quality and is frequently assessed using waiting times, which are referred to as "patient-centered metrics" (Frochle & Magazine, 2013). In the medical field, waiting time is usually defined as the amount of time spent in the examination room and office, or the amount of time that passes between checking in at the front desk and seeing the doctor. Low patient satisfaction is a result of longer wait times for patients in emergency departments (Haraden

& Resar, 2011). The two main aspects of the quality of health care services that are correlated with patient satisfaction and waiting times are the technical and interpersonal aspects. According to Dagger et al. (2007), technical quality is the knowledge, skill, and proficiency of a service provider.

Since patient satisfaction is a major factor in determining patients' viewpoint behavioral intention and provides information on the provider's performance in satisfying clients' expectations, it is a crucial indicator of the quality of healthcare. The healthcare sector has to deal with issues including staff turnover, a rapidly changing environment, and higher client expectations. This business and the manufacturing sector are comparable in that workers in both deal with intricate processes to deliver goods or provide customer service. Because it offers a business a competitive edge, the healthcare sector must be concerned about employee happiness. Customer happiness is greatly impacted by employees in the service business, particularly when they engage with customers. Employee productivity and organizational citizenship may both rise when workers are satisfied. Additionally, a high employee satisfaction rate can minimize medical mistake rates and other costs associated with unethical behavior, such as those related to hiring, reputation management, legal fees, and attrition (Collins, 2011).

The five components of the patient experience in a healthcare organization—medical, admission, overall, social responsibility, and discharge services—are used to gauge the quality of healthcare services (Aagja & Garg, 2010). In addition to health care assessment, factors including professionalism, empathy, the physical environment, and the connection between the employee and the patient should be taken into account (Arasli et al, 2008). A study on patient satisfaction and behavior intention in private hospitals in Malaysia found that all service factors have a positive relationship with patient satisfaction and that the three dimensions of service quality—tangible, assured, and empathic—have a significant relationship with patients' intention to use hospital services going forward (Wan & Nor, 2016). According to research, patient satisfaction is crucial in healthcare settings because it can be used to gauge the quality of care received and to foster trust between the hospital and its clients (Salisbury, Burgess, Lattimer, Heaney, Walker, Turnbull & Smith, 2015; Moliner, 2009). Patients often return to the same hospital for care after developing a close attachment over time; this is referred to as patient loyalty (Kessler & Mylod, 2011). In the healthcare sector, patient happiness is closely linked to the caliber of treatment that a provider provides. However, because customer assessment is dependent on behaviors and attitudes, healthcare quality is elusive and hard to quantify. Therefore, in order to be competitive in the market, healthcare providers must continuously improve the quality of their healthcare services in terms of hospitality provided by medical staff, equipment, and technology. According to Asma et al. (2016), rising living standards have led to higher consumer expectations, making it harder for healthcare providers to satisfy their patients. The Significance of Contented Workers According to Omar and Zakaria (2016), employee satisfaction is the state of contentment, pleasant emotions, and motivation gained from work tasks. A higher level of happiness among employees directly correlates with productivity, which in turn improves the patient experience. The social factor (supervisor and peer), the individual factor (personality, marital status, and age), the job task (autonomy, benefits, and challenges), and the organizational factor (corporate culture, work procedures, and technologies) were the factors that Pantouvakis and Mpogiatzidis (2013) proposed as influencing employee satisfaction.

2.1.8 Waste reduction

Using less material and energy to reduce trash output and protect natural resources is known as waste reduction. Reduced energy consumption from more efficient product development and use leads to lower pollution levels

(Davidson, 2011). A collection of procedures and methods known as waste reduction aim to lessen the quantity of garbage that is generated. Waste minimization aids in the promotion of a more sustainable society by lowering or eliminating the production of hazardous and persistent wastes. Redesigning goods and procedures as well as altering society consumption and production patterns are all part of waste reduction (Davidson, 2011). Compared to recycling, waste reduction is more comprehensive as it includes strategies for keeping materials from becoming waste before they are recycled (James, 2018). Reusing items like dishrags in place of paper towels, buying more sturdy goods, and reusing materials like plastic and glass containers are all examples of waste reduction strategies. Donating goods lowers the total quantity of material produced, including apparel, office supplies, and eyewear. Buying items with biodegradable chemicals instead of toxic ones lowers waste and pollution. Waste reduction generally has a number of positive effects on the environment (James, 2018). Reduced energy consumption from more efficient product manufacture and use leads to lower pollution levels. There are more natural resources protected. There are products that employ less dangerous ingredients. Ultimately, landfills receive less solid trash. Reducing waste also results in financial savings. When waste-reduction techniques are implemented, fewer materials and energy are consumed. A cradle-to-cradle system is used in place of the conventional cradle-to-grave methodology. Products in this so-called "cradle-to-cradle," or "industrial ecology," system are not utilized for a limited period of time. Products are passed on for other uses rather than having materials or component parts disposed away after a single use. This is seen as a material flow. This may be cooperatively implemented both inside an organization and between organizations that might otherwise be seen as unconnected. For instance, an upholsterer receives the leftover material from a cotton producer and utilizes it to fill chairs. When the chair reaches the end of its life, the materials are sent back to the maker, who repurposes the pieces with durability. The non-hazardous materials used to construct the damaged upholstery are sold to a nearby farmer who composts it. Additionally, money is saved by making fewer purchases. Less materials become waste, which lowers trash-disposal costs. Individuals, companies, organizations, towns, government agencies, and institutions like hospitals or schools may all minimize waste. There are several methods that people can reduce their waste: (1) Product reuse. This might entail refilling water bottles or recycling file folders rather than tossing them away after one use; (2) Making better use of things. This might include photocopying on both sides of the paper; and (3) giving away or trading goods or commodities that could appear pointless to one person but could be valuable to another. For instance, after recycling the more durable components of the old chairs, the chair manufacturer previously described had no internal use for the waste upholstery. But because to a cooperative arrangement with a nearby farmer, the leftovers might be put to new use, helping the farmer by boosting his compost (Underwood, 2018).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the Hollman's Model theory.

The Hollman's Model suggests that management by objectives facilitates effective communication between principal and teachers in order to achieve the objectives and targets that have been set by the organization. This model consists of a number of the following distinctive steps: Identification of managers' key areas of job responsibility; establishment of specific objectives in each key area of responsibility; periodic review of progress toward objectives and end-of-period evaluation of managers' performance on objectives. This model identified that the managers' assessments of MBO effectiveness were measured in terms of seven MBO effectiveness dimensions namely; planning and organizing work, objective method of evaluating work performance, motivation of the best performance, coordination of individual and work group objectives, improvement in manager-

employee communication, improvement in manager-employee cooperation and overall satisfaction with MBO (Hollmann, 2013).

2.3 Empirical Review

Asmus, Karl, Mohnen, Reinhast, (2015), conducted a study on the influence of goal-setting on worker performance in an industrial production process. For empirical examination, we conducted a real-effort experiment at the Training Factory for Energy Productivity at the Technische Universität München. The number and quality of the assembled goods were checked, and the amount of compressed air used for each completed good was also recorded, in order to gauge the participants' performance. Four groups in all, each in a distinct experimental environment, were defined. As the first experiment of its kind on goal-setting in an industrial production context, the findings of this one will be of great use to scholars and practitioners working in the subject of sustainable manufacturing. The main findings show that goal-setting enhances worker performance by 12 to 15% when compared to the absence of objectives, even in the absence of financial incentives. This holds true for the groups which had to maximize either output quantity or output quality, as well as for the group which was obliged to be as energy efficient as possible.

Teo and Low (2016), conducted a study on the Impact of Goal Setting on Employee Effectiveness to Improve Organisation: Empirical study of a High-Tech Company in Singapore, this paper presents the results of a business research project conducted by the researchers in XYZ (Singapore) Pte Ltd, which is a Hi-Tech semiconductor test systems and equipment company in Singapore. The research question is: "Does goal setting have an impact on employee effectiveness and ultimately improves organization effectiveness?" The researcher created a conceptual model that explains goal-setting and how it relates to both organizational and personnel success. A qualitative investigation was used to assess the validity and reliability of the three hypotheses developed for this study. The three hypotheses and their connections are sufficiently supported by the evidence found in the literature study and search. To investigate the three hypotheses, an empirical study was conducted in XYZ Singapore. There are explanations given for the study approach used as well as the study's theoretical and empirical value. Also emphasized are pertinent ethical concerns with the data collecting process. The results of this empirical study indicated that the three tested hypotheses are visible in their organization and are valid and dependable. The research interviewees all agreed that goal-setting influences employee performance, which in turn enhances organizational success, and that it plays a part in the link shown in the conceptual model.

Cecere and Corrocher, (2016), conducted a study on Stringency of regulation and innovation in waste management: an empirical analysis on EU countries the transformation of waste into a valuable resource is a key process towards sustainable development and green growth and therefore represents a major concern for policy-makers. Waste management greatly benefits from technological innovation, thus it is important to comprehend how regulations may encourage innovation in this area. This paper examines the dynamic link between environmental regulation stringency and innovation in a cross-country European scenario, with the goal of verifying the weak form of the Porter hypothesis in waste management. The findings show that regulations with higher levels of stringency have a favorable impact on innovation; however, this effect is non-linear, indicating that there may be an ideal level of regulation. Moreover, the nation's general environmental state and the existence of heavily polluting industries impede the advancement of environmental advances.

Townsend,(2019), Waste is a global composite of organic and inorganic derivatives from human activities. Municipal solid waste consists primarily of plastics from households and e-wastes, creating opportunities for

waste management businesses. This study set out to investigate leadership techniques for cutting operational expenses in Liberian waste management companies. Six company executives from six waste management companies in Liberia were chosen as participants for this multiple case study. The transformational leadership theory served as the study's conceptual foundation. Open-ended questions were asked during a semi-structured interview with each business leader. Recurrent codes were iteratively searched in order to extract themes from the data. Themes that surfaced were efficiency and effectiveness in creating value out of trash, as well as education and training for both employees and customers. The results of this study suggest that leaders in the waste management industry might help bring about social change by hiring underrepresented groups in their local communities. By employing waste management technology advancements to enhance their abilities and messaging, underprivileged groups within communities might be given the confidence to spread waste management messages about recycling. The study's findings may help waste management executives employ creative approaches to reuse, recycle, and repurpose wastes. The findings of this study may be able to assist executives in the waste management industry in identifying ways to enhance the quality of life for consumers and staff members through waste-to-energy goods and services.

Methodology

This study employed the descriptive survey design. Both primary and secondary sources of data were used in the study. The area of study has to do with geographical area, language, and general culture. The area of this study is Enugu state. The hospital institution understudy was Parklane, G.R.A. Enugu. The target population of the study consist of one thousand, one hundred and fifty-one (1,151), with a sample of 288 determined for the study using Freund and Williams's statistical formula at 5 percent margin of error.

Given the objectives and the nature of the study, the study made use of questionnaire administration. The questionnaire was designed and administered on the selected respondents in the hospital. The responses generated were used thereafter for data analysis. The responses from the participants were measured using 5-liket scale as follows: Strongly Agree [SA] –5 points, Agree A – 4 points, Undecided UN – 3 Points, disagree [D] – 2 points and strongly Disagree SD – 1 point.

Data were collected, coded, grouped into frequencies, and arranged into tables for ease of reference. Data from the questionnaire were collected and analyzed using simple percentages and mean. To determine the nature and strength of relationship between the research variables, Pearson correlation (r) was used to test the hypotheses.

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 The relationship between setting objectives and the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu

Table 4.1.1. Responses to research question one on the relationship between setting objectives and the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		
1	Setting objectives provides direction and specific area to attain	475	256	48	32	41	852	3.48	1.506	Agree
		95	64	16	29	41	245			
		38.8	26.1	6.5	11.8	16.7	100%			
2	Clearer focus on what is vital is ensured	360	256	75	36	66	793	3.24	1.594	Agree
		72	64	25	18	66	245			
		29.4	26.1	10.2	7.3	26.9	100%			
3	There is sense of personal satisfaction if you create goals	410	308	78	40	40	876	3.58	1.437	Agree
		82	77	26	20	40	245			
		33.5	31.4	10.6	8.2	16.3	100%			
4	Possible control of the future facilitates the job	480	276	21	84	31	892	3.64	1.458	Agree
		96	69	7	42	31	245			
		39.2	28.2	2.9	17.1	12.7	100%			
5	Setting goals motivate employees and set targets for the hospital	450	276	54	40	48	868	3.54	1.527	Agree
		90	69	18	20	48	245			
		36.7	28.2	7.3	8.2	19.6	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.496	1.5044	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1, 159 respondents out of 245 representing 64.9 Setting objectives provides direction and specific area to attain 3.48 and standard deviation of 1.506. Clearer focus on what is vital is ensured 136 respondents representing 55.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.24 and standard deviation of 1.594. There is sense of personal satisfaction if you create goals 159 respondents representing 64.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.58 and standard deviation of 1.437. Possible control of the future facilitates the job 141 respondents representing 67.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.84 and 1.458. Setting goals motivate employees and set targets for the hospital 159 respondents representing 64.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.54 and standard deviation of 1.527.

4.1.2 The relationship between developing action plans and the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu
Table 4.1.2 Responses to research question two on the relationship between developing action plans and the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu

		5	4	3	2	1	∑FX	-	SD	Decisio
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		n
1	Action plan allows teams of the hospital to be on the top of their tasks	455 91 37.1	320 80 35.	21 7 2.9	88 44 18.	15 15 6.1	899 245 100%	3.67	1.279	Agree
2	Effective coordination and communication requirement are enhanced to all stakeholders	360 72 29.4	352 88 35.	3 1 .4	76 38 15.	46 46 18.8	837 245 100%	3.42	1.509	Agree
3	Action plan breaks down the goal into actionable steps that can be easily followed	400 80 32.7	360 90 36.	18 6 2.4	80 40 16.	29 29 11.8	887 245 100%	3.62	1.390	Agree
4	The action plan clarify what resources are required to reach the goals	400 80 32.7	296 74 30.	69 23 9.4	12 6 2.4	62 62 25.3	839 245 100%	3.42	1.573	Agree
5	Ownership and accountability are created by action plan	505 101 41.2	236 59 24.	42 14 5.7	86 43 17.	28 28 11.4	897 245 100%	3.66	1.447	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.55	1.4396	8

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.2, 171 respondents out of 245 representing 73.0 the action plan allows teams of the hospital to be on the top of their task 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.279. Effective coordination and communication requirement are enhanced to all stakeholders’ 160 respondents representing 65.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.42 and standard deviation of 1.509. Action plan breaks down the goal into actionable steps that can be easily followed 170 respondents representing 69.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.62 and standard deviation of 1.390. The action plan clarify what resources are required to reach the goals 154 respondents representing 62.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.42 and 1.573. Ownership and accountability are created by action plan 160 respondents representing 65.3 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.66 and standard deviation of 1.447.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis one: Setting objectives have relationship with the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu.

Table 4.2.1.: Pearson correlation matrix – test on setting objectives have relationship with the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu

Correlations		Setting objectives provides direction and specific area to attain	Clearer focus on what is vital is ensured	There is sense of personal satisfaction if you create goals	Possible control of the future facilitates the job	Setting goals motivate employees and set targets for the hospital
Setting objectives provides direction and specific area to attain	Pearson Correlation	1	.673**	.662**	.576**	.592**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
Clearer focus on what is vital is ensured	Pearson Correlation	.673**	1	.577**	.456**	.450**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
There is sense of personal satisfaction if you create goals	Pearson Correlation	.662**	.577**	1	.577**	.769**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
Possible control of the future facilitates the job	Pearson Correlation	.576**	.456**	.577**	1	.648**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
Setting goals motivate employees and set targets for the hospital	Pearson Correlation	.592**	.450**	.769**	.648**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision Rule

If the calculated r-value is greater than the critical r -value (i.e. $r_{cal} > r_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

The correlation coefficient shows $.450 < .673$. and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents that setting objectives had positive significant relationship with the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu

Decision

Table 4.2.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on setting objectives and the operational efficiency showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. From the correlation coefficient shows $.450 < .673$, this value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that setting objectives had positive significant relationship with the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu, ($r = .450 < .673$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .450 < .673, p < .05$).

4.2.2 Hypothesis two: Developing action plans have relationship with the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu

Table 4.2.2.: Pearson correlation matrix – test on developing action plans have relationship with the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu

Correlations		Action plan allows teams of the hospital to be on the top of their tasks	Effective coordination and communication requirements are enhanced to all stakeholders	Action plan breaks down the goal into actionable steps that can be easily followed	The action plan clarify what resources are required to reach the goals	Ownership and accountability are created by action plan
Action plan allows teams of the hospital to be on the top of their tasks	Pearson Correlation	1	.719**	.718**	.580**	.585**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
Effective coordination and communication requirements are enhanced to all stakeholders	Pearson Correlation	.719**	1	.732**	.581**	.587**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245

Action plan breaks down the goal into actionable steps that can be easily followed	Pearson Correlation	.718**	.732**	1	.584**	.565**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
The action plan clarify what resources are required to reach the goals	Pearson Correlation	.580**	.581**	.584**	1	.479**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	245	245	245	245	245
Ownership and accountability are created by action plan	Pearson Correlation	.585**	.587**	.565**	.479**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	245	245	245	245	245

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Decision Rule

If the calculated r-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e. $r_{cal} > r_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

Pearson correlation matrix (r) – value of $.479 < .719$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents that developing action plans had positive significant relationship with the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated r- value of $.479 < .719$ against the critical r - value of 2.18 (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that developing action plans had positive significant relationship with the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu

5.1 Summary of findings

- i. Setting objectives had positive significant relationship with the operational efficiency of Parklane hospital, Enugu $r(95, n = 245), .450 < .769 = p. < 0.05$
- ii. Developing action plans had positive significant relationship with the waste reduction of Parklane hospital Enugu $r(95, n = 245), .479 < .719 = p. < 0.05$

5.2 Conclusion

The study on management by objectives and performance of Parklane hospital Enugu concluded that setting objectives and developing action plans, had positive significant relationship with the operational efficiency and waste reduction. Successful management of MBO system implies managing situations, thus no one managerial tool could be panacea to achieve the best management performance. Management by Objectives (MBO) is a managerial tool that has been successfully applied in many work settings of organizational planning and operation. Goal management increases the incentive of workers to work and to accomplish organizational objectives.

Organizational goals and planning flow top-down through the organization and are translated into personal goals for organizational members

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for study

- i. Organizations objective should be stated to all employees at the initial time of recruitment in other to avoid lapses.
- ii. The Organizational strategy should be flexible and adaptable in other to enhance performance and productivity

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